

LiftWEC

DEVELOPMENT OF A NEW CLASS OF WAVE ENERGY CONVERTER
BASED ON HYDRODYNAMIC LIFT FORCES

Deliverable D4.7

Open access experimental data from 3D scale model

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

After a successful experimental test campaign of the LiftWEC two-dimensional model in Ecole Centrale de Nantes (ECN) in June and July 2021, a three-dimensional model of the LiftWEC concept was tested in September and October 2022. The 3D model was designed, built, assembled and commissioned by ECN. The dataset associated with the experimental measurements was uploaded on Zenodo with DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669668>. The model tested is composed of one or two hydrofoils rotating around a horizontal axis, perpendicular to the wave direction. The model was tested in a range of regular and irregular seas. The data contains time series measurements of the model in the wave tank including; wave elevation, rotor angular position, forces on the hydrofoils, torque on the power take off and position of the hexapod holding the model. This data is the second set of wave tank data generated for the LiftWEC H2020 research project. The first set consisted of results for a similar device tested in 2D, while this second set contains results for tests conducted in 3D. For a complete description of the 3D testing and dataset, readers are directed to "*LiftWEC Deliverable D4.8. Report on physical modelling of 3D LiftWEC concepts*" with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7669625. The dataset for the 2D testing experimental measurements was uploaded on Zenodo with DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5534471>

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document attests of the publication of the experimental 3D model testing open source dataset on online repository Zenodo, with DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669668>. This document provides essential information on the experimental testing carried out and the published data to facilitate the use of the data. The full description of the test campaign and data collected is available in "*LiftWEC Deliverable D4.8. Report on physical modelling of 3D LiftWEC concepts*" with DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669625>

2 MODEL TESTING SETUP

A close-up view of the 3D model, fabricated for the LiftWEC project, outside the tank is shown in Figure 2-1. The full setup in the wave tank is shown in Figure 2-2 and Figure 2-3. It includes the 3D LiftWEC model, a tripod structure to support a six degree motion hexapod (or Stewart platform). The LiftWEC model is supported under the hexapod.

A schematic of the setup in the tank is shown in Figure 2-4.

Figure 2-1: Overview of the 3D LiftWEC model outside the tank

Figure 2-2: Overview of the 3D LiftWEC model in the tank, under the hexapod

Figure 2-3: Overview of the 3D LiftWEC model in the tank, under the hexapod

Figure 2-4: Schematic of the tank and model setup

3 TEST MATRIX

The test matrix in this section provides the final information on the list of tests carried out during the test campaign. It includes the wave characteristics, model configuration and PTO control strategy. The test matrix is presented in appendix A and gives all parameters required for data analysis. Represented columns are:

- **Test num:** The unique test number, which is used in all the project reports, data files, etc.
- **Wave type:** type of wave generated during the test, it may be:
 - IN AIR: model test outside the tank
 - Calib: if the wave type contains this word, the test is a wave calibration test
 - ZERO: model in water but no wave generated
 - RW = Regular waves
 - PW = Polychromatic waves, containing five regular wave components.
 - IW = Irregular waves (Jonswap spectrum)
- **WaveCalibTestNum:** test number in which the same wave characteristics were calibrated

- **IW_Seed:** Irregular wave seed, corresponding to a given random phase modifier to convert the wave spectrum to a wave time series. Each seed number correspond to a given wave time series.
- **T/Tp(s):** wave period (regular) or Peak period (irregular)
- **H/Hs(m):** wave height (regular) or Significant wave height (irregular)
- **Foil1 phase:** Requested phase angle between wave peak and foil 1 position at quarter cord. In fixed rotor position tests, this gives the fixed position of the rotor for all the test duration. The phase is positive when foil 1 is at its highest position after the wave peak is at the centre of the model.
- **RotorPeriod:** Duration in seconds for one full rotation of the rotor
- **Vrotor_Rad_sec:** Rotor speed in constant speed mode
- **Rotor motion profile:** rotational velocity profile of the rotor. This can be:
 - **Constant:** the rotor speed is constant during all test after reaching its set speed
 - **Fixed:** the rotor shaft did not move during the test
 - **LinAcc 1 or 2 or 3:** This is an acceleration controlled mode in which the rotor accelerates slowly, stays at a set speed for some time and then decelerates slowly. Three motion profiles were tested.
 - **Control 2 or 4:** this is a variable speed test with a motion time series repeated each wave period.
- **Foils on model:** Number of foils on mode
- **Rot axis initial depth:** Depth of the rotor axis at the start of each test. This remained fixed except when “model motion profile” is not “zero”.
- **Initial Orientation [°]:** Angle between the model and the wave direction (yaw). Zero degree means the rotor axis of rotation is perpendicular to the wave direction
- **Model motion profile:** Profile of the motion set by the hexapod.
- **Model motion phase:** phase of the model motion.
- **End plates:** True when end plates are placed at the end of the foil(s)
- **Pitch1:** Foil 1 angle value, “False” means this foil is not on the model
- **Pitch2:** Foil 2 angle value, “False” means this foil is not on the model
- **Comments:** Any comment or observation during the test

4 TEST FILE

After testing, a Matlab code developed by ECN was used to merge the three data files into a single file including all the calibrated parameters sampled at 128 Hz and in SI units. The data processing done to merge all data files is:

- Open the three raw data files generated by the two acquisition systems, the CRio and Quantum.
- Select channels that need to be save for data analysis

- Find the rising edge of the wavemaker trigger signal in all data files and change the time reference to zero value at the corresponding line in the time series. The rising edge also corresponds to the start of wave generation.
- Resample the time series at the desired acquisition rate of 128Hz for this project.
- Save all selected channels in a single file.

It then generated for each test a Matlab and a text file (only the text file is available in the dataset). The name of the merged file is "LIFTWEC3D_XXX", with XXX the test number described in the test matrix (see appendix A). It contains a Matlab structure with the following elements (the text file contains the same elements in the headers, except "II" and "Type", followed by the numerical data):

- "date": test date in Matlab number format
- "data": test data with one column per parameter
- "Time": time column corresponding to the "data" table. In this column, zero value corresponds to the first time step in which the wavemaker trigger value is high, which means the wavemaker is starting.
- "chanNames": name of the header for each column in the "data" table.
- "chanUnits": SI units corresponding to each column in the "data" table.
- "testnum": Test number corresponding to the list of tests in the test matrix as explained in section 3.
- "family": All sensors are sorted in families to simplify the analysis with the ECN Matlab code. This may not be required for further analysis
- "II": This element is used in the ECN Matlab code to find a column in the "data" element corresponding to a given sensor. This may not be required for further analysis
- "type": This element is used in the ECN Matlab code to choose the type of analysis to be done for each test. This may not be required for further analysis

During wave calibration, the list of channels in the data elements and listed in "chanNames" are:

- 2 columns with water temperature and conductivity.
- 1 columns with wavemaker trigger in Volts. This column is not needed for further analysis, it was used to synchronise the data files.
- "WGx": 10 columns with Wave gauges (WG) 1 to 10 measurement in meter. "x" is the wave gauge number.

During model testing, the list of channels in the data elements and listed in "chanNames" are:

- 2 columns with water temperature and conductivity.
- 2 columns with wavemaker trigger in binary format and in Volts. These columns are not needed for further analysis, they were used to synchronise the data files.
- "WGx": 10 columns with Wave gauges (WG) measurements in meter (WG5 was removed and the WG5 data should not be used). X is the wave gauge number.
- "Fx": 8 columns with force measurement (F) in Newton from the 8 load cells on the model. "x" is the load cell number.

- “Speed”: The rotor speed in radian per second
- “Motortorque”: The motor estimated torque in Newton meter.
- “Torquemeter”: The torque measured at the torque meter in Newton meter.
- “Cpt_position_aux”: The rotor position in degree.

Details on the instrumentation are in section 5.

In addition to the data collected in the merged files, described in section **Error! Reference source not found.**, the processed data with corrected loads and torques was added in new columns after the merged data. These new columns are calculated from the raw measurement, the load and torque zeroing described in section **Error! Reference source not found.**, the deduction of the centrifugal force on the load cells described in section **Error! Reference source not found.** and the friction compensation on the torque value described in section **Error! Reference source not found.**.

The list of additional channels in the “data” elements and listed in “chanNames” are:

- “Fx_Cor”: 8 columns with force measurement, adjusted by removing the zero values and the centrifugal force. “x” is the load cell number
- “Motortorque_Cor”: The motor estimated torque in Newton meter adjusted by removing the zero values.
- “Torquemeter_Cor”: The torque measured in Newton meter at the torque meter adjusted by removing the zero values
- “TorqueAtFoil_Cor”: The corrected torque (Torquemeter_Cor) with, in addition, the friction compensation.

Details on the instrumentation and acquisition system are in section **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.**.

The name of the merged file for each test is “LIFTWEC3D_XXX_CorSC.mat”, with XXX the test number described in the test matrix.

More details on the data files are available in “*LiftWEC Deliverable D4.8. Report on physical modelling of 3D LiftWEC concepts*” with DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7669625>

5 DESCRIPTION OF SENSORS AND MEASURED PARAMETERS

5.1 WAVE GAUGES

Ten wave gauges, measuring water surface elevation, were deployed in the tank for wave calibration, with the model installed at its test location without hydrofoils. The list of wave gauges and locations are in Table 5-1 and illustrated in Figure 5-1. This setup allows measurement of the reflected waves in front and behind the model with four wave gauges aligned at the centre of the basin either side of the model. In addition, one wave gauge placed beside the model, in the direction perpendicular to the wave propagation direction, gives a wave measurement at the same distance from the paddles.

During testing with the active part of the model (rotor, foils, etc.), wave gauge 5 was removed to leave space for the rotation of the foils.

Wave gauge ID	Wave gauge length (m)	Position X (m) (distance to paddles)	Position Y (m) (Relative to basin centreline)	Comments
1	0.6	14.95	0	
2	0.6	15.10	0	
3	0.6	15.45	0	
4	0.6	16.15	0	
5	0.6	17.15	0	Wave calibration only
6	0.6	18.15	0	
7	0.6 <td 18.3	0		
8	0.6	18.65	0	
9	0.6	19.35	0	
10	0.6	17.15	3	

Table 5-1: Position of wave gauges in the basin (model scale)

Figure 5-1 : Illustration of wave gauges position in the basin.

All wave gauges were calibrated before installation in the basin, with the same cables and acquisition system as used during tank testing. The calibration rig is outside the basin and composed of a controlled linear actuator and a tank filled with water pumped from the basin to ensure same water conductivity.

5.2 LOAD CELLS

Eight load cells measured the load applied from the two foils on the rotor arms. Two are located on either side of each foil and measure the load in radial and tangential directions. The list of load cells and their measured parameter is in Table 5-2.

Sensor	Direction	Side	Foil
F1	Radial	Motor	1
F2	Tangential	Motor	1
F3	Radial	Motor	2
F4	Tangential	Motor	2
F5	Radial	Collector	1
F6	Tangential	Collector	1
F7	Radial	Collector	2
F8	Tangential	Collector	2

Table 5-2: List of load cells and measured parameter

The description of measured radial and tangential forces is shown in [Figure 5-2](#). The loads are measured at a distance of a quarter of the foil cord length from the leading edge and the direction of the radial force is parallel to a line passing through the axis of rotation and the centre of the foil (half foil cord). The radial force is positive when the force applied by the foil on the rotor is directed away from the centre of rotation. The tangential force is positive when the force applied by the foil on the rotor is directed towards the leading edge, in this direction the foil is accelerating the rotor or generating power.

Figure 5-2: Illustration of radial and tangential force measured by the load cells

The load cells selected are manufactured by the German company HBK, see picture in [Figure 5-3](#). The models details are:

- K-Z6-F-C3-0050-N-S3-N (+/-500N capacity) for the radial direction
- K-Z6-F-C3-0030-N-S3-N (+/-300N capacity) for the tangential direction

Figure 5-3: Picture of a load cell used during the experiments

All load cells were checked before installation on the model and were calibrated once on the model with final cabling structure, through the arms and slip ring.

5.3 PTO TORQUE TRANSDUCER

A torque transducer with a torque rating of 100Nm, measures the torque on the motor shaft. It is produced by the German company ETH-messtechnik and the model is DRBK II 100 A. The sensor is located in the motor dry enclosure and in series between the motor shaft and the main rotor shaft holding arms and foils.

The torque transducer could not be calibrated at ECN and the measurements are based on the sensor datasheet and the factory certificate.

Figure 5-4: Picture of the torque transducer used during the experiments

5.4 ANGULAR POSITION

A magnetic encoder measures the rotor angular position, it is placed in the dry enclosure on the slip ring side of the model. The moving part is attached to the shaft in line with the motor and torque meter and it has a resolution of 4096 pulses per turn, corresponding to an angular resolution of 0.09 degree. The encoder is produced by the German company Automation Sensorik Messtechnik (ASM). The magnetic disk model is PMIR5-50-64-M-83-AB and that of the reader head is PMIS4-50-64-20KHZ-TTL-Z3-3M-S

The encoder has a reference position, which is used to calibrate the absolute position measurement. When the encoder is turned on, the absolute position is not known but when the reference position is sensed (after one turn maximum) the acquisition system corrects the measured value to the known position of the reference. This action was done before testing, each time the acquisition system was restarted, and therefore does not affect the acquired files, which always give the absolute position.

The angle value is zero when the line passing through the centre of the rotor and the centre of the foil (half of the cord length) is vertical and the foil 1 is at its highest position. The recorded value is wrapped between 0 and 360 degrees.

5.5 HEXAPOD MOTION

The hexapod operates with its own software, independent to all other control and acquisition equipment in the basin. Its motion measurement, derived from the six electrical motors positions, cannot be logged and synchronised with other measurements. Therefore, the model motion, when the hexapod is running, was measured using Qualisys motion cameras. This approach also has the advantage that there is no risk of a wrong transfer function between motor positions and actual model six-degree position.

The Qualisys camera system was composed of three cameras placed under the tripod, each one under one leg of the tripod. Four markers were placed on top of the hexapod moving plate at locations visible from all the three cameras. See [Figure 5-5](#). This allowed the generation of a rigid body to measure all six-degree motions of the model.

Figure 5-5: Moving plate of the hexapod, above the model, with Qualisys reflective markers

5.6 VIDEO CAMERAS

Two PTZ CCTV camera, with HD resolution and an optical zoom of x25, recorded video in all model tests, these were starting with the wavemaker trigger. An underwater video camera was placed at the bottom of the tank (on the incoming wave side). The camera and its waterproof housing are shown in [Figure 5-6](#). The second camera was placed above water surface.

Figure 5-6: Underwater video camera used in the experiments

6 APPENDICES

A. TEST MATRIX

Test num	Wave type	W_Calib_TestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
Inertia testing in air																		
72	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
73	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
74	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
75	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
76	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
77	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
78	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
79	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
80	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
81	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-8	False	
92	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
93	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
94	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
95	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
96	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
82	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
83	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
84	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
85	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
86	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	4	False	
87	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
88	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
89	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
90	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
91	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		False	-12	False	
102	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
103	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
104	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
105	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils
106	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	This test is same as with two foils

Test num	Wave type	W CalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
107	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
108	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
109	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
110	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
111	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
97	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
98	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
99	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
100	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
101	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	0	False	This test is same as with two foils
112	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
113	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
114	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
115	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
116	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
117	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
118	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
119	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
120	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
121	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	1	0	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
92	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
93	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
94	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
95	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
96	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	0	0	
72	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
73	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
74	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
75	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
76	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		False	-4	4	
97	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
98	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
99	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
100	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
101	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
102	IN AIR				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
103	IN AIR				-		3.2	1.963495408	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
104	IN AIR				-		1.6	3.926990817	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
105	IN AIR				-		0.8	7.853981634	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
106	IN AIR				-		0.523598776	12	Constant	2	0	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
PLACE MODEL IN WATER WITHOUT FOILS																		
Wave Calibration																		
132	RW			1.4008	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
133	RW			1.6000	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
134	RW			1.8028	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
135	RW			2.0000	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
136	RW			2.2022	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
137	RW			2.4038	0.15				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
138	RW			2.0000	0.10				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Regular waves calculated to have a repeat time of 1024sec
151	PW			2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
152	PW			2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
154	IW		Seed2	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	Seeds 1 and 3 gave low quality spectrum (test discarded)
155	IW		Seed4	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
156	IW		Seed5	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
157	IW		Seed6	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	low quality spectrum (test discarded)
158	IW		Seed7	2.50	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
147	IW		Seed1	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
148	IW		Seed2	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	low quality spectrum (test discarded)
149	IW		Seed3	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
150	IW		Seed4	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
153	IW		Seed5	2.10	0.16				fixed	0	0.6	0	ZERO		False	False	False	
ADD FOIL1, SWITCH TO -4DEG PITCH																		
159	ZERO			-			62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
218	ZERO			-			62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat
162	ZERO			-			0.799998129	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
163	ZERO			-			1.400933179	4.485	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
164	ZERO			-			1.599996259	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
165	ZERO			-			1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
167	ZERO			-			1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
168	ZERO			-			2.202308204	2.853	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
169	ZERO			-			2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
177	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
254	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat
176	ZERO				-		1.599996259	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
171	ZERO				-		1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
172	ZERO				-		1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
173	ZERO				-		2.202308204	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
175	ZERO				-		2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
192	ZERO				-		1.802922613	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	these had to be changed to match the regular waves exact period
193	ZERO				-		2.403666912	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
178	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
179	ZERO				-		1.599996259	3.927	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
180	ZERO				-		1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
181	ZERO				-		1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
182	ZERO				-		2.202308204	2.853	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
185	ZERO				-		2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
214	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
215	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
216	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
Reg Waves																		
187	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
188	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
194	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
190	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
191	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
195	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
196	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
197	RW	135		2.00	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
198	RW	135		2.00	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
199	RW	135		2.00	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
253	RW	72		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat
256	RW	76		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat
FORCE FLOW SEPARATION BY PHASE SHIFT																		
200	RW	133		1.60	0.15	90	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
201	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
202	RW	137		2.404	0.15	90	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	
252	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		False	-4	False	repeat

Test num	Wave type	WCalbTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	FoilI phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
SUBSTRUCTURE MOTION TEST																		
224	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p118	0	False	-4	False	
226	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p118	-45	False	-4	False	
230	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p118	-90	False	-4	False	
237	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	0	False	-4	False	
238	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-45	False	-4	False	
247	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-90	False	-4	False	
248	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-180	False	-4	False	
233	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	0	False	-4	False	
234	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-45	False	-4	False	
235	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-90	False	-4	False	
236	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-180	False	-4	False	
249	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T1p98_A0p375	0	False	-4	False	Rotor speed is 2rad/sec instead of 1.98
250	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T1p98_A0p375	0	False	-4	False	Rotor speed is 2rad/sec instead of 1.98
251	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T1p98_A0p075	0	False	-4	False	Rotor speed is 2rad/sec instead of 1.98
SWITCH TO END PLATES, REMAIN AT -4DEG PITCH																		
270	ZERO						62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
271	ZERO						0.80000	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
272	ZERO						1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
273	ZERO						1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
274	ZERO						1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
275	ZERO						2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
276	ZERO						2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
295	ZERO						3.20081	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
277	ZERO						62.83185	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
278	ZERO						0.80000	7.854	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
279	ZERO						1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
280	ZERO						1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
281	ZERO						1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
283	ZERO						2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
284	ZERO						2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
257	ZERO						62.83185	0.1	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
258	ZERO						1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
259	ZERO						1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
267	ZERO						1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
268	ZERO						2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
269	ZERO						2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
296	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
297	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
298	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
Reg Waves																		
285	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
286	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
287	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
288	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
289	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
290	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
291	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
292	RW	135		2.00	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
293	RW	135		2.00	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
294	RW	135		2.00	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	False	
ADDED REPETITION OF Substructure tests with PLATES AND FOIL1 PHASE = 270																		
299	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	0	False	-4	False	
300	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-45	False	-4	False	
301	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-90	False	-4	False	
302	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-180	False	-4	False	
304	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	0	False	-4	False	
305	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-45	False	-4	False	
306	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-90	False	-4	False	
307	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-180	False	-4	False	
SWITCH TO -8 DEG PITCH																		
314	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
315	ZERO				-		0.80000	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
316	ZERO				-		1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
317	ZERO				-		1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
318	ZERO				-		1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
319	ZERO				-		2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
320	ZERO				-		2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
321	ZERO				-		3.20081	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
325	ZERO				-		62.83185	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
326	ZERO				-		1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
327	ZERO				-		1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
328	ZERO				-		1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
329	ZERO				-		2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
330	ZERO				-		2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
308	ZERO				-		62.83185	0.1	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
309	ZERO				-		1.60000	3.927	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
310	ZERO				-		1.79982	3.491	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
311	ZERO				-		1.99974	3.142	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
312	ZERO				-		2.20231	2.853	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
313	ZERO				-		2.39816	2.62	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
322	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
323	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
324	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
Reg Waves																		
331	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
332	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
333	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
334	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
335	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
336	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
337	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
338	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
339	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
340	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
FORCE FLOW SEPARATION BY PHASE SHIFT																		
341	RW	133		1.60	0.15	90	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
342	RW	135		2.00	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
343	RW	137		2.404	0.15	90	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	
FREE WHEELING TEST																		
344	RW	137		2.404	0.15	Free	Free	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-8	False	Started with constant speed and rotor stopped quickly after motor shutdown
ADJUST HEXAPOD YAW ANGLE																		
346	RW	133		1.60	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	15	ZERO		True	-8	False	
347	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	15	ZERO		True	-8	False	
349	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	15	ZERO		True	-8	False	
350	RW	133		1.60	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	30	ZERO		True	-8	False	
351	RW	135		2.00	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	30	ZERO		True	-8	False	
352	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	30	ZERO		True	-8	False	
POLYCHROMATIC WAVE MODE																		
353	PW	151		2.10	0.16	90	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	-8	False	
354	PW	152		2.50	0.16	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	-8	False	
ROTOR FIXED POSITION																		
348	RW	137		2.404	0.15	90		0	fixed	1	0.6	15	ZERO		True	-8	False	

Test num	Wave type	W_Calib_TestNum	IW_Seed	T/Trp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Wrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
SWITCH TO 0 DEG PITCH																		
355	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
356	ZERO				-		0.799998129	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
357	ZERO				-		1.599996259	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
358	ZERO				-		1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
359	ZERO				-		2.00	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
360	ZERO				-		2.20	2.853	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
361	ZERO				-		2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
362	ZERO				-		3.200807594	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
377	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
378	ZERO				-		1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
371	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
372	ZERO				-		1.60	3.927	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
373	ZERO				-		1.799823921	3.491	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
374	ZERO				-		1.999740709	3.142	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
375	ZERO				-		2.20	2.853	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
376	ZERO				-		2.398162331	2.62	Constant	1	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
Reg Waves																		
379	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
380	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
381	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
382	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
383	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
384	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
385	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
386	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
387	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
388	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
ROTOR FIXED POSITION																		
391	RW	136		2.202	0.15	0		0	fixed	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
392	RW	136		2.202	0.15	180		0	fixed	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
FORCE FLOW SEPARATION BY PHASE SHIFT																		
389	RW	134		1.803	0.15	90	1.803	3.485	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
390	RW	136		2.202	0.15	90	2.202	2.853	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
363	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
364	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	
365	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
POLYCHROMATIC WAVE MODE																		
394	PW	151		2.10	0.16	270	1.60	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
395	PW	152		2.50	0.16	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
IRREGULAR WAVE MODE																		
396	IW	154	Seed2	2.50	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
397	IW	155	Seed4	2.50	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
398	IW	156	Seed5	2.50	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
399	IW	158	Seed7	2.50	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
400	IW	154	Seed2	2.50	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
401	IW	155	Seed4	2.50	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
402	IW	156	Seed5	2.50	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
403	IW	158	Seed7	2.50	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
404	IW	154	Seed2	2.50	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
405	IW	155	Seed4	2.50	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
406	IW	156	Seed5	2.50	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
408	IW	158	Seed7	2.50	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
409	IW	154	Seed2	2.50	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
410	IW	155	Seed4	2.50	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
411	IW	156	Seed5	2.50	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
412	IW	158	Seed7	2.50	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
413	IW	147	Seed1	2.10	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
414	IW	149	Seed3	2.10	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
415	IW	150	Seed4	2.10	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
416	IW	153	Seed5	2.10	0.16		4.999	1.257	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
417	IW	147	Seed1	2.10	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
418	IW	149	Seed3	2.10	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
419	IW	150	Seed4	2.10	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
420	IW	153	Seed5	2.10	0.16		6.997	0.898	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
421	IW	147	Seed1	2.10	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
422	IW	149	Seed3	2.10	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
423	IW	150	Seed4	2.10	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
424	IW	153	Seed5	2.10	0.16		3.999	1.571	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
425	IW	147	Seed1	2.10	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
426	IW	149	Seed3	2.10	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
427	IW	150	Seed4	2.10	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
428	IW	153	Seed5	2.10	0.16		3.300	1.904	Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	SpecialWaveDef	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Red_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments	
SWITCH TO -12 DEG PITCH																			
434	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
437	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
438	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
439	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
440	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																			
445	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
446	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
447	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
448	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																			
441	ZERO				-				LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
443	ZERO				-				LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	Undervoltage
444	ZERO				-				LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-12	False	
Reg Waves																			
456	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
457	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
458	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
459	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
460	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
461	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
462	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-12	False		
SWITCH TO 4 DEG PITCH																			
489	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
490	ZERO				-		0.800	7.854	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
491	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
492	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
493	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
494	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	1	0.755	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																			
463	ZERO				-		62.832	0.100	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
464	ZERO				-		0.800	7.854	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
465	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
466	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
467	ZERO				-		2.398	2.620	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		
468	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False		

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
Reg Waves																		
POSITION CONTROL MODE																		
473	RW	133		1.600	0.15	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
474	RW	135		2.000	0.15	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
475	RW	138		2.000	0.10	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
482	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
483	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
484	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
485	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
486	RW	138		2.000	0.10	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
488	RW	138		2.000	0.10	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	4	False	
SWITCH TO 0 DEG PITCH																		
495	ZERO				-		62.83185307	0.1	Constant	1	0.6	0	ZERO		True	4	False	
496	RW	133		1.600	0.15	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
497	RW	135		2.000	0.15	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
498	RW	138		2.000	0.10	90			Constant	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
499	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
500	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
501	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	PTO undervoltage
503	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	PTO undervoltage, freewheeling after
506	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	PTO undervoltage, freewheeling after
502	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
504	RW	138		2.000	0.10	Var			Control-2	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
505	RW	138		2.000	0.10	Var			Control-4	1	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	False	
SWITCH TO 0 DEG PITCH																		
513	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
514	ZERO				-		0.800	7.854	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
515	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
516	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
517	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
518	ZERO				-		2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
519	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
520	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
524	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
525	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
526	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
527	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
528	ZERO				-		2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
530	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
573	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	

Test num	Wave type	WCalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
507	ZERO				-		62.832	0.1	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
508	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
509	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
510	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
511	ZERO				-		2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
512	ZERO				-		2.398	2.62	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
521	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
522	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
523	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
Reg Waves																		
531	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
532	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
533	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
534	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
535	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
536	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
537	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
538	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
539	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
540	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
552	RW	135		2.000	0.15	90	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
568	RW	72		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
569	RW	74		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
570	RW	76		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
SUBSTRUCTURE MOTION TEST																		
558	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	0	True	0	0	
560	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-45	True	0	0	
561	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-90	True	0	0	
562	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p375	-180	True	0	0	
563	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	0	True	0	0	
564	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-45	True	0	0	
565	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-90	True	0	0	
566	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075	-180	True	0	0	
FOIL COMPLIANCE TESTING																		
571	RW	135		2.000	0.15		2.00	3.141592654	Constant	2	0.6	0	Struct-4	10	True	0	0	short test
572	RW	135		2.000	0.15		2.00	3.141592654	Constant	2	0.6	0	Struct-4	10	True	0	0	problem with rotor position sensor?
567	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.00	3.141592654	Constant	2	0.6	0	T2p0_A0p075 surge only	10	True	0	0	

Test num	Wave type	W_CalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1_phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
FREE WHEELING TEST																		
553	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
554	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
555	RW	137		2.404	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	0	0	
ROTOR FIXED POSITION																		
549	RW	136		2.202	0.15	0		0	Constant	2	0.6		Zero		True	0	0	
550	RW	136		2.202	0.15	90		0	Constant	2	0.6		Zero		True	0	0	
551	RW	136		2.202	0.15	180		0	Constant	2	0.6		Zero		True	0	0	
556	RW	136		2.202	0.15	0		0	Constant	2	0.755		Zero		True	0	0	
557	RW	136		2.202	0.15	90		0	Constant	2	0.755		Zero		True	0	0	
IRREGULAR WAVE MODE																		
541	IW	154	Seed2	2.500	0.16		3.3	1.903995548	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
542	IW	155	Seed4	2.500	0.16		3.3	1.903995548	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
543	IW	156	Seed5	2.500	0.16		3.3	1.903995548	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
544	IW	158	Seed7	2.500	0.16		3.3	1.903995548	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
545	IW	147	Seed1	2.100	0.16		5	1.256637061	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
546	IW	149	Seed3	2.100	0.16		5	1.256637061	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
547	IW	150	Seed4	2.100	0.16		5	1.256637061	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
548	IW	153	Seed5	2.100	0.16		5	1.256637061	Constant	2	0.6	0	Zero		True	0	0	
MOUNT FOIL 2, SWITCH TO -4 DEG PITCH																		
587	ZERO						62.832	0.100	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
588	ZERO						1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
589	ZERO						1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
590	ZERO						2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
591	ZERO						2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
592	ZERO						2.398	2.620	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
593	ZERO						3.201	1.963	Constant	2	0.755	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
597	ZERO						62.832	0.100	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
598	ZERO						1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
599	ZERO						1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
600	ZERO						2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
601	ZERO						2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
602	ZERO						2.398	2.620	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
574	ZERO						62.832	0.100	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
575	ZERO						1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
576	ZERO						1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
577	ZERO						2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
578	ZERO						2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	
579	ZERO						2.398	2.620	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO		True	-4	4	

Test num	Wave type	W/CalibTestNum	IW_Seed	T/Tp(s)	H/Hs(m)	Foil1 phase	Rotor period	Vrotor_Rad_sec	Rotor motion profile	Foils on model	Rot axis initial depth	Initial Orientation [°]	Model motion profile	Model motion phase	End plates	Pitch1	Pitch2	Comments
580	ZERO				-		62.832	0.100	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		repeat
584	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		repeat
585	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	2	0.5	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		repeat
ACCELERATION CONTROL MODE																		
594	ZERO				-			LinAcc-1	LinAcc-1	2	0.755	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
595	ZERO				-			LinAcc-2	LinAcc-2	2	0.755	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
596	ZERO				-			LinAcc-3	LinAcc-3	2	0.755	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
Reg Waves																		
603	RW	132		1.401	0.15	270	1.401	4.485	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
604	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
605	RW	134		1.803	0.15	270	1.803	3.485	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
606	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
607	RW	136		2.202	0.15	270	2.202	2.853	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
608	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
609	RW	135		2.000	0.15	225	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
610	RW	135		2.000	0.15	180	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
611	RW	135		2.000	0.15	315	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
612	RW	135		2.000	0.15	0	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
FORCE FLOW SEPARATION BY PHASE SHIFT																		
613	RW	133		1.600	0.15	270	1.600	3.927	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
614	RW	135		2.000	0.15	270	2.000	3.142	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
615	RW	137		2.404	0.15	270	2.404	2.614	Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
FREE WHEELING TEST																		
616	RW	133		1.600	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
617	RW	135		2.000	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
618	RW	137		2.404	0.15	Free	Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
619	IW	155	Seed4	2.500	0.16		Free		Constant	2	0.6	0	ZERO	True	-4	4		
Substructure drag																		
622	ZERO				-		62.832	0.100	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
623	ZERO				-		0.800	7.854	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
624	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
625	ZERO				-		1.800	3.491	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
626	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
627	ZERO				-		2.202	2.853	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
628	ZERO				-		2.398	2.620	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
629	ZERO				-		3.201	1.963	Constant	0	0.755	0	Zero	False	False	False		
ADJUST SUBMERGENCE																		
630	ZERO				-		62.832	0.100	Constant	0	0.5	0	Zero	False	False	False		
631	ZERO				-		1.600	3.927	Constant	0	0.5	0	Zero	False	False	False		
632	ZERO				-		2.000	3.142	Constant	0	0.5	0	Zero	False	False	False		
633	ZERO				-		2.398	2.620	Constant	0	0.5	0	Zero	False	False	False		